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Competitiveness management of enterprises under martial law

The subject of the research the theoretical aspects of managing the competitiveness of Ukrainian enterprises under martial law.

The aim of the research is to determine the main strategies for managing the competitiveness of enterprises under martial law and the factors influencing their effective management.

Research methods. In writing the article, various research methods were used, in particular: literature and secondary data analysis; SWOT analysis; PESTEL analysis; case study method; comparative analysis; scenario analysis method; dynamic analysis method; tabular and graphical method, etc.

Results of the investigation. It is established that in the context of modern global challenges, one of the most important aspects of the country's economic development is the ability of enterprises to

maintain and develop their competitiveness. It is proved that hostilities lead to a decrease in economic activity, destruction of infrastructure, and instability in markets, which significantly affects the ability of enterprises to remain competitive. It is found that the competitiveness of an enterprise is determined by its ability to successfully operate in a market economy, maintain its market position and ensure sustainable development. The main obstacles to the competitiveness of enterprises as a result of hostilities on the territory of Ukraine are identified: destruction of infrastructure; labor migration; disruption of logistics chains; financial instability; and reduced demand. It is established that among the main factors influencing the management of competitiveness of enterprises in wartime are: economic factors; political and legal factors; social factors; technological factors. The main strategies for increasing competitiveness in wartime are proposed: diversification of sales and supply markets; digitalization and implementation of innovations; strategic risk management; adaptation of products to new conditions; support for national initiatives and integration with international programs. It is established that the state also supports the competitiveness of Ukrainian enterprises, namely: financial assistance; protection of strategic enterprises; regulatory support; support for innovation

Scope of the results. *Enterprise management, enterprise competitiveness, strategic development, enterprise economics.*

Conclusions. *It has been determined that in the conditions of martial law, the management of the competitiveness of enterprises in Ukraine is becoming critically important for their survival and further development. Adaptation to new conditions, diversification of markets, digitalization of business processes and active support from the State are key elements that contribute to maintaining the competitiveness of enterprises. Effective risk management and flexibility in strategies will allow Ukrainian companies not only to avoid the obstacles caused by the war, but also to ensure sustainable development in the post-war period. The key factors affecting this process are economic instability, political and legal restrictions, social changes, and technological challenges. In order to maintain competitive positions, it is necessary to implement strategies of diversification, cost optimization, increased flexibility and the use of the latest technologies. It is also established that military conflicts create a special context in which enterprises must adapt to new conditions in order to remain viable and effective in the market. It is proved that the war significantly changes all aspects of economic activity, including business operations, enterprise management and competitiveness strategies.*

Keywords: *management, competitiveness, enterprises, martial law, strategies, factors, state.*

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Управління конкурентоспроможністю підприємств в умовах воєнного стану

Предметом дослідження є теоретичні аспекти управління конкурентоспроможністю українських підприємств в умовах воєнного стану.

Метою дослідження є визначення основних стратегій управління конкурентоспроможністю підприємств в умовах воєнного стану та чинників впливу на їх ефективне управління.

Методи дослідження. При написанні статті було використано різні методи дослідження, зокрема: аналіз літератури та вторинних даних; SWOT-аналіз; PESTEL-аналіз; метод кейсів; порівняльний аналіз; метод сценарного аналізу; метод динамічного аналізу; таблично-графічний метод та ін.

Результати роботи. Встановлено, що в умовах сучасних глобальних викликів, одним із найважливіших аспектів економічного розвитку країни є здатність підприємств зберігати та розвивати свою конкурентоспроможність. Доведено, що воєнні дії призводять до зниження економічної активності, руйнування інфраструктури, нестабільності на ринках, що суттєво впливає на можливості підприємств залишатися конкурентоспроможними. З'ясовано, що конкурентоспроможність підприємства визначається його здатністю успішно діяти в умовах ринкової економіки, утримувати свої позиції на ринку та забезпечувати сталий розвиток. Визначено основні перешкоди в результаті воєнних дій на території України по відношенню до конкурентоспроможності підприємств: руйнування інфраструк-

ЕКОНОМІЧНІ ПРОБЛЕМИ РОЗВИТКУ ГАЛУЗЕЙ ТА ВИДІВ ЕКОНОМІЧНОЇ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ

тури; міграція робочої сили; порушення логістичних ланцюгів; фінансова нестабільність; зниження попиту. Встановлено, що серед основних чинників, які впливають на управління конкурентоспроможністю підприємств у воєнний час є: економічні чинники; політичні та правові чинники; соціальні чинники; технологічні чинники. Запропоновано основні стратегії підвищення конкурентоспроможності в умовах війни: диверсифікація ринків збуту та постачання, цифровізація та впровадження інновацій; стратегічне управління ризиками; адаптація продукції до нових умов; підтримка національних ініціатив та інтеграція з міжнародними програмами. Встановлено, що держава також підтримує конкурентоспроможність українських підприємств, а саме: фінансова допомога; захист стратегічних підприємств; регуляторна підтримка; підтримка інноваційної діяльності.

Галузь застосування результатів. Управління підприємствами, конкурентоспроможність підприємств, стратегічний розвиток, економіка підприємства.

Висновки. Визначено, що в умовах воєнного стану управління конкурентоспроможністю підприємств в Україні стає критично необхідним для їхнього виживання та подальшого розвитку. Адаптація до нових умов, диверсифікація ринків, цифровізація бізнес-процесів та активна підтримка з боку держави є ключовими елементами, що сприяють збереженню конкурентоспроможності підприємств. Ефективне управління ризиками та гнучкість у стратегіях дозволяють українським компаніям не лише уникнути перешкод спричинених війною, але й забезпечити стійкий розвиток у післявоєнний період. Ключовими чинниками, що впливають на цей процес, є економічна нестабільність, політичні та правові обмеження, соціальні зміни та технологічні виклики. Для збереження конкурентних позицій необхідно впроваджувати стратегії диверсифікації, оптимізації витрат, підвищення гнучкості та використання новітніх технологій. Також, встановлено, що військові конфлікти створюють особливий контекст, у якому підприємства повинні пристосовуватись до нових умов, щоб залишатись життєздатними та ефективними на ринку. Доведено, що війна суттєво змінює всі аспекти економічної діяльності, включаючи функціонування бізнесу, управління підприємствами та стратегії їх конкурентоспроможності.

Ключові слова: управління, конкурентоспроможність, підприємства, воєнний стан, стратегії, чинники, держава.

Formulation of the problem. In today's global challenges, one of the most important aspects of the country's economic development is the ability of enterprises to maintain and develop their competitiveness. Military actions lead to a decline in economic activity, destruction of infrastructure, and instability in markets, which significantly affects the ability of companies to remain competitive.

In the context of military aggression in Ukraine, companies are forced not only to maintain their positions in the domestic and foreign markets, but also to respond quickly to external threats, risks of losing markets and disrupting supply chains. Changes in consumer behavior, rising logistics costs, and a shortage of human and material resources pose new challenges for businesses, which require the development of flexible and effective strategies. In such circumstances, it is crucial to ensure rapid adaptation, efficient use of resources, innovation and digitalization. In addition, companies should consider not only the short-term goals of their existence but also formulate long-term strategies for recovery and development in

the post-war period. Thus, the relevance of competitiveness management under martial law lies in the need to develop new management strategies that will allow enterprises not only to survive in crisis conditions, but also to use the available opportunities for their development and strengthening of market positions in the post-war period.

Analysis of research and publications on the problem. The research on managing the competitiveness of enterprises under martial law is a relatively new and specific topic, especially for Ukraine. However, some authors and researchers both in Ukraine and abroad have already studied similar issues, in particular in times of crisis, instability or conflict. Among the main authors whose works can be useful for understanding competitiveness management during martial law are: M. Porter – his classic theories of competitive advantage and enterprise competitiveness are the basis for many studies in this area. Although his works are focused on general market conditions, the principles of adaptation to complex conditions can be applied to crisis and conflict conditions; Fukuyama – studied the impact of so-

cial trust and institutions on economic development, which may be relevant for understanding how enterprises adapt to weak or changed institutional conditions during war; Dolishnyi and Karpenko – in the Ukrainian context, studied the competitiveness of enterprises in conditions of crisis and instability, including during war. Their works focus on risk management, adaptation of business models and search for new markets; Hrytsak O. P. – studied the specifics of economic development in Ukraine in the context of hybrid wars, emphasizing the importance of adaptability of enterprises and state support to maintain their competitiveness; T. Friedman – in his works covers global processes and their impact on national economies, including the topics of conflicts and their impact on market structures, which also relates to competitiveness during the crisis; Melnyk O. – studied the issue of the These authors have laid the theoretical and practical basis for understanding how enterprises can maintain and strengthen their competitiveness during military conflicts and instability, which is important for further research in this area.

Presenting main material. The competitiveness of an enterprise is determined by its ability to successfully operate in a market economy, maintain its market position and ensure sustainable development. Traditional theories of competitiveness focus on factors such as innovation, production efficiency, product quality, and the ability to strategize and develop. However, in wartime, these factors are influenced by the external environment (armed conflicts, disruption of supply chains, economic instability, etc.) [1; 2; 3; 4; 5].

The war that began in Ukraine in 2022 created unprecedented obstacles for Ukraine’s economy, the largest of which are as follows (Table 1) [6; 7; 8]:

The main factors that influence the management of the competitiveness of enterprises in wartime include the following [9; 10; 11]:

1. Economic factors – economic instability in the regions affected by the war, which causes sharp changes in financial flows, inflation and exchange rates. Here, businesses are forced to respond to: rising costs of resources, including raw materials and energy; disruptions in delivery schedules, which increase transportation costs, etc.; changes in consumer interests due to a decrease in the purchasing power of the population and the priority of spending on basic needs.

2. Political and legal factors – restrictions on movement and trade in the war zone; changes in legislation, in particular on taxation, labor relations and business regulation; risk of nationalization of assets or their destruction as a result of hostilities.

3. Social factors – mass migration of the population, which leads to the loss of qualified personnel and changes in the structure of the labor market; increased stress among employees and the inability to ensure proper working conditions in dangerous conditions; changes in consumer priorities, where part of the market is redirected to support military needs and basic means of survival.

4. Technological factors – military conflicts affect the ability of enterprises to introduce the latest technologies and modernize production processes: disruption of access to new technologies and imports of equipment; reduced investment in research and innovation due to the overall decline in the investment climate; adaptation of existing technologies to new realities, including the creation of more mobile and autonomous production systems, etc.

Table 1. Negative effects of the war in Ukraine on businesses

№	The barrier	Characteristics.
1	Destruction of infrastructure	Armed hostilities have destroyed production facilities, transportation infrastructure and logistics chains, reducing the ability of businesses to maintain production processes at a high level
2	Migration of labor force	The war has forced millions of people to flee their homes, resulting in a shortage of skilled workers in many industries, which leads to a loss of labor, complicating production processes and reducing the competitiveness of enterprises
3	Disruption of logistics chains	Due to the closure of ports, the destruction of transportation routes and sanctions, Ukrainian companies have faced difficulties in securing raw materials and components
4	Financial instability	Economic instability and currency fluctuations have increased the cost of imported goods and complicated access to investment
5	Decrease in demand	Military actions caused a general decline in consumer demand both in the domestic and foreign markets, which weakened the competitiveness of enterprises

Fig. 1. Strategies to improve competitiveness in wartime

In order for companies to maintain their competitiveness, it is necessary to implement new strategies to improve competitiveness in the war (Fig. 1) [12; 13; 14]:

The state also plays an important role in creating favorable conditions for maintaining the competitiveness of Ukrainian enterprises in times of war. Thus, the main areas of state support may include: financial assistance (provision of subsidies, low-interest loan programs and support for small and medium-sized businesses); protection of strategic enterprises (direct state intervention to support enterprises of strategic importance for the country's economy); regulatory support (facilitation of simplification of bureaucratic procedures for export and import of goods, support for integration into international trade blocs); support for innovation (creation of programs to stimulate innovation, in particular in the defense industry) [15; 16; 17; 18; 19; 20].

Conclusions

In the context of martial law, managing the competitiveness of enterprises in Ukraine becomes critical for their survival and further development. Adaptation to new conditions, market diversification, digitalization of business processes, and active support from the state are key elements that help companies maintain their competitiveness. Successful risk management and flexibility in strategies will allow Ukrainian companies not only to avoid the obstacles caused by the war, but also to ensure sustainable development in the post-war period. The key factors affecting this process are economic instability, political and legal restrictions, social changes, and technological challenges. To maintain a competitive position, it is necessary to implement strategies for diversification, cost optimization, increased flexibility and the use of the latest technologies. In addition, military con-

flicts create a special context in which businesses must adapt to new conditions to remain viable and effective in the market. War significantly changes all aspects of economic activity, including business operations, enterprise management and competitiveness strategies.

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